

A Study on Health and Wellness among College Students

Dr. Shelar Vikas Sudhakar

Director of Physical Education and Sports, Late. K. G. Kataria College, Daund, Pune

Corresponding Author – Dr. Shelar Vikas Sudhakar

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Abstract:

Health and wellness play a significant role in the overall development of college students. In today's modern lifestyle, students are often exposed to various health-related challenges such as stress, unhealthy eating habits, lack of physical activity, and excessive use of digital devices. The present study aims to examine the health and wellness status of college students and understand the influence of lifestyle habits on their physical and mental well-being. The study was conducted using the survey method, and data were collected from 60 college students through a structured questionnaire. The analysis was carried out using percentage and mean statistical methods. The findings reveal that while a majority of students participate in sports activities, many students do not engage regularly in physical exercise and do not follow a balanced diet. The study also found that talking with friends is the most common method used by students to manage stress. Additionally, a significant number of students spend considerable time using mobile phones and the internet. The study concludes that promoting regular physical activity, balanced nutrition, and stress management practices is essential to improve the health and wellness of college students.

Keywords: *Health, Wellness, College Students, Physical Activity, Mental Health, Lifestyle.*

Introduction:

In today's modern lifestyle, many factors affect the health of students. Stress, unhealthy dietary habits, lack of physical activity, and excessive use of digital devices are impacting students' health. Health and Wellness refers to maintaining a balance of physical, mental, social, and emotional well-being. If college students maintain good health, it helps improve their academic performance and overall personality development.

Need for the Study:

Increasing stress, unhealthy lifestyle patterns, and lack of exercise among college students make it necessary to understand their health status. Therefore, the need for health and wellness programs has become very important.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the health status of college students.
2. To evaluate the physical and mental health of students.
3. To understand the impact of students' lifestyle on their health.
4. To suggest health and wellness programs for students.

Hypothesis:

- Students who exercise regularly have better health.
- Students who consume a balanced diet have better fitness levels.
- Mental stress affects the health of students.

Research Method:

The present study was conducted to examine the **health and wellness status of college students**. For this purpose, the **survey method** of research was adopted as it is suitable for collecting information from a large group of respondents regarding their lifestyle, health habits, and well-being.

The study was carried out among **60 college students** selected from the college. The sample included students from different classes and backgrounds in order to obtain a general understanding of their health and wellness status.

Components of Health and Wellness:

The following components are important in students' health and wellness:

Physical Health- Regular exercise Participation in sports
Balanced diet

Mental Health- Stress management, Positive thinking, Meditation and yoga,

Social Health- Good relationships with friends, Participation in social activities,

Emotional Health- Control over emotions, Self-confidence

How many days per week do you exercise?

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	Every day	18	30
2	3–4 days a week	10	17
3	Occasionally	00	33
4	Never	12	20
	Total	60	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows the frequency of exercise among college students. Out of the total 60 students, 18 students (30%) reported that they exercise every day, while 10 students (17%) exercise 3–4 days a week. The highest number of

students, 20 students (33%), stated that they exercise occasionally. In addition, 12 students (20%) reported that they never exercise.

Do you participate in sports activities?

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	Yes	42	70
2	No	18	30

Interpretation

The above table shows the participation of students in sports activities. Out of the total 60 students, 42 students (70%) reported that they participate in sports activities, while 18 students (30%) stated that they do not participate in sports activities.

How much time do you spend on physical activity daily?

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	30 minutes	14	23
2	1 hour	16	26
3	2 hours	08	14
4	None	22	37
	Total	60	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows the daily time spent on physical activity by college students. Out of 60 students, 14 students (23%) spend 30 minutes on physical activity, while 16 students (26%) spend 1 hour daily. Only 8 students (14%) reported spending 2 hours on physical activity. However, a large number of students, 22 students (37%), reported that they do not engage in any physical activity.

Do you follow a balanced diet?

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	Always	12	20
2	Sometimes	12	20
3	Rarely	04	7
4	Never	32	53
	Total	60	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows whether students follow a balanced diet. Out of 60 students, 12 students (20%) reported that they always follow a balanced diet, while 12 students (20%) stated that they sometimes follow a balanced diet. Only 4 students (7%) said that they rarely follow a balanced diet. However, a large number of students, 32 students (53 %), reported that they never follow a balanced diet.

Part 2: Mental Health:**Do you feel stress due to studies?**

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	High	06	10
2	Moderate	10	16
3	Low	16	27
4	Not at all	28	47
	Total	60	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows the stress levels experienced by students due to their studies. Out of 60 students, 6 students (10%) reported experiencing high stress, while 10 students (16%) reported moderate stress. 16 students (27%) indicated that they experience low levels of stress. However, the majority of students, 28 students (47%), reported that they do not experience stress at all due to their studies.

What do you do to reduce stress?

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	Exercise	16	27
2	Yoga / Meditation	12	20
3	Talk with friends	26	43
4	Nothing	06	10
	Total	60	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows the methods used by students to reduce stress. Out of 60 students, 16 students (26%) reported that they reduce stress through exercise, while 12 students (20%) use yoga or meditation. The majority of students, 26 students (43 %), prefer talking with friends as a way to relieve stress. However, 6 students (10%) reported that they do nothing to manage their stress.

Do you get enough sleep?

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	Yes	60	100
2	No	0	0

Interpretation:

The above table shows whether students get sufficient sleep. Out of the total 60 students, all 60 students (100%) reported that they get sufficient sleep, while no students (0%) reported a lack of sufficient sleep.

Part 3: Lifestyle:**How much time do you spend using mobile/internet daily?**

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	1–2 hours	16	27
2	3–4 hours	12	20
3	5–6 hours	26	43
4	More than 6 hours	06	10
	Total	60	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows the amount of time students spend using mobile phones or the internet each day. Out of 60 students, 16 students (27 %) use mobile/internet for 1–2 hours, while 12 students (20%) use it for 3–4 hours daily. The majority of students, 26 students (43%), reported using mobile/internet for 5–6 hours per day. Additionally, 6 students (10%) spend more than 6 hours daily on mobile or internet usage.

Do you undergo regular health check-ups?

Sr. No.	Particulars	Student Response	Percentage
1	Yes	60	100
2	No	0	0

Interpretation:

The above table shows the awareness of students about Health and Wellness. Out of the total 60 students, all 60 students (100%) reported that they are aware of Health and Wellness, while no students (0%) reported that they are unaware of it.

Conclusion:

- Students who exercise regularly show better physical fitness.

- Many students are not regularly involved in physical activities.
- A large number of students do not follow a balanced diet.
- Talking with friends is the most common method used to reduce stress.
- Students spend a significant amount of time using mobile and internet devices.
- Participation in sports, exercise, and yoga contributes to better health and wellness among students.

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